

Topic 2: Silicon Photovoltaics
Subtopic: 2.3 Heterojunction Solar Cells
Oral presentation preferred

PROCESSING ROUTES AND COSTS FOR COPPER PLATING ON BIFACIAL HETEROJUNCTION CELLS

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Introduction and Motivation

Copper electroplating is considered to be the future metallization technique for solar cells as it offers the advantages of very low material price, highly conductive narrow lines and low processing temperatures. However, while plating is often used for high efficiency devices [1], its integration in mass production remains behind expectations because of higher process complexity compared to screen printing, requirements for investments in new technology and uncertainties in reliability. The share of plating in mass production is supposed to be at 5% in 2019 [2].

We discuss the main available processing routes for Cu plating on heterojunction and other carrier selective contact solar cells and compare on selected processes the cost for plating in relation to screen printing for soldered ribbons and for interconnection with conductive adhesives.

We present our approach for simultaneous plating on both sides of bifacial cells. This approach benefits from a seed layer deposition and inkjet masking to have sufficient conductivity for galvanic co-plating and to result in reproducible, reliable and narrow Cu contacts. Alternatives, potentially simplifying the plating process are discussed and will be further studied until the conference.

It is shown that the formed Cu contacts can be reliably interconnected in modules by soldering interconnection ribbons to plated busbars or by applying multi-wire technologies such as SmartWire interconnection. It will be shown that even for very low plated Cu thickness efficient and reliable interconnection is feasible. Thus plating throughput can be increased and cost further reduced.

With the seed layer process we have achieved 24.1% efficiency on an industrial precursor with a 4-BB-layout on both sides and with double antireflective coating on the front. This result has been independently confirmed (aperture area 225 cm²) [3]. Recently 24.3% were measured internally and let anticipate that with adapted metallization layout efficiencies of 24.5% can be achieved.

Approach and Conclusions

SmartWire interconnection is often used for heterojunction cells. It eases the constraints on finger conductivity, allows for fine-line printing and tremendous reduction in silver paste consumption [4] but requires investment in new equipment.

For standard interconnection with soldered ribbons of bifacial cells with 4 busbars the consumption of (low T) silver paste is very high, up to 400 mg per cell, as for sufficient adhesion and module stability thick busbars have to be printed. If electrically conductive adhesive (ECA) is used for interconnection the silver paste consumption is reduced by almost 50% since the adhesive can be applied directly on TCO and busbars are not necessary. However here the cost for the ECA has to be taken into account. Further reduction in paste consumption is achieved by increasing the number of busbars but also the amount of ECA needed for interconnection increases.

For the process cost calculation we use numbers from our project partners like cell or equipment manufacturers, research institutes, having also pilot production lines, from literature [5, 6] and numbers based on our own processing experience. For single process steps like patterning mask removal and seed layer etch-back bottom-up calculations are made according to SEMI standards [7].

The cost for plating on bifacial cells with 4 busbars is in the same range as for screen printing including conductive adhesive while plating offers the possibility to use also the standard technology with soldered ribbons. Plating is used in production already for IBC cells and enables reduction of the number of cell segments for shingling as plating of thick highly conductive lines does not significantly increase the process cost.

EXPLANATORY PAGES

Processing Routes

With a thin conductive oxide on top the main process route for heterojunction cells, including structures with intrinsic tunnel oxide or conductive passivation layers [8], is deposition of a seed layer blanket, patterning mask (with different technologies), plating of copper and a solderable capping layer, mask removal and seed layer etch-back [9 - 11]. In figure 1 the processing route currently applied at CSEM, with a copper seed layer and patterning by inkjet printing of a hotmelt ink, is depicted.

Fig. 1. (a) Copper seed layer blanket on TCO with a hotmelt-inkjet mask, (b) after Cu plating and after mask removal and seed layer etch-back (c).

Different approach has been used by Tetrasun with patterning of the seed layer and dielectric deposition over the entire surface serving as a plating mask [12]. Similar sequence with a printed seed – grid, followed by dielectric deposition and plating, has also been described [13, 14]. Furthermore it is possible to deposit

at first a dielectric layer on the TCO and form the seed – grid by transferring a NiV layer from a foil by laser [15].

A very interesting technology having the potential to simplify the plating process for all solar cell types and to fully eliminate costly patterning is the selective electrochemical deposition with micro-nozzles, so-called Dynamic Liquid Meniscus [16]. However, this technology is still in development.

Cost comparison

In figure 2 the cost of screen printing for bifacial cells with 4 busbars for soldered ribbons and 4 – 6 busbars for interconnection with conductive adhesive is compared with our baseline plating process comprising PVD seed layer blanket, patterning by hotmelt inkjet printing, plating, mask removal and seed layer etch-back. For the PVD seed layer two options are calculated: the seed layer is deposited in the same equipment as the TCO by adding a chamber and targets for deposition on both sides. The second option is a separate PVD tool for seed layer deposition, which increases the cost but improves the process safety.

The cost for screen printing is split in two blocks: cost for silver paste and all other costs comprising equipment, depreciation, floor space, utilities and waste, consumables and labor (Europe). The calculation is based on numbers from pilot production and on a silver paste and ECA price for high volume customer.

The cost for patterning for plating has also been split in two blocks: ink consumption and all the other cost for equipment, depreciation, floor space, utilities and waste, consumables and labor. The number for ink consumption is based on own experience and a price for high volume customer. The cost for plating originates from a manufacturer of plating equipment and is backed by production experience (for 20 μm copper and 3 - 4 μm electroplated tin).

Fig. 2. Cost comparison of screen printing for interconnection with soldered ribbons or electrically conductive adhesive (ECA) and plating process with PVD seed layer and hotmelt inkjet (HMI) patterning for bifacial heterojunction cells

Recent cell and module results at CSEM

For SmartWire interconnection we have tested the influence of line thickness on reliability and prepared cells with copper thickness between 2 and 17 μm . We have used a copper seed layer sputtered directly on TCO. Even though photoluminescence measurements of substrates annealed with copper seed layer confirm the ability of TCOs to prevent copper diffusion into the cell the final proof for reliability has to be done on module level. Details of processing have been described previously [3, 17].

Extended aging tests of 1-cell glass-backsheet modules show good stability after more than 450 TC and 2800 hours DH, which is more than 2x the requirement in IEC61215 norm. In fig. 3 the results for modules with InSn wires are shown. The Voc is stable confirming good cell stability, the best fill factor stability is measured for copper thickness above 5 μm , which may be influenced by the pyramid size of cell precursors (big pyramids, $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$). The same trend is observed for modules with In-free wires (not shown here).

Figure 3. Voc and FF degradation of 1-cell SmartWire modules with InSn300wires.

With a modified seed layer comprising an adhesion layer peel forces above 1 N/mm busbar width were measured on different substrates (table 1) and first module tests with soldered ribbons show very good stability after 200 TC and 1000h DH ($\sim 1\%$ degradation, glass-glass 1-cell modules).

Precursor type	Busbars	Ribbon	F_{aver} [N]	$F_{\text{aver}} / 1\text{mm BB-width}$ [N]
M2 ps (ITO)	4BB 0.8 mm	1.0 mm	5.6	5.6
M0 ps (ITO)	4BB 1.7 mm	1.7 mm	6.8	4.0

Table 1. Peel force on different substrates, ribbons with SnPbAg coating, soldering temperature 240°C

As an alternative route, in order to reduce patterning cost, a process with printed seed-grid and a dielectric as plating mask will be investigated.

References

- [1] D. Adachi, J. L. Hernández and K. Yamamoto, "Impact of carrier recombination on fill factor for large area heterojunction crystalline silicon solar cell with 25.1% efficiency", Applied Physics Letters 107 (2015)

- [2] ITRPV International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic, 8th Edition, 2017, p. 12
- [3] A. Lachowicz, J. Geissbühler, A. Faes, J. Champliand, F. Debrot, E. Kobayashi, J. Horzel, C. Ballif, M. Despeisse, "Copper Plating Process for Bifacial Heterojunction Cells", 33rd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Amsterdam, 2017
- [4] P. Papet, L. Andretta, D. Lachenal, G. Wahli, J. Meixenberger, B. Legradic, W. Frammelsberger, D. Bätzner, B. Strahm, Y. Yao and T. Söderström, "New cell metallization pattern for heterojunction solar cells interconnected by the Smart Wire Connection Technology", Energy Procedia, 2015
- [5] A. Louwen, W. van Sark, R. Schropp, A. Faaij, „A cost roadmap for silicon heterojunction solar cell“, Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, 2016
- [6] R. Russel, L. Tous, E. Cornagliotti, D. Hendrickx, F. Duerinckx, J. Szlufcik, „Simultaneous Fabrication of n & p Contacts for Bifacial Cells by a Novel Co-plating Process“, 33rd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Amsterdam, 2017
- [7] SEMI, VDMA, "Total Cost of Ownership in PV Manufacturing Guide", October 2013, (Revised February 2014), <http://www.itrpv.net/Reports/Downloads/Related-documents>
- [8] O. Schultz-Wittmann, A. Turner, B. Eggleston, D. De Ceuster, D. Suwito, E. van Kerschaver, S. Baker-finch and Victor Prajapati, "High Volume Manufacturing of High Efficiency Crystalline Silicon Solar Cells with Shielded Metal Contacts", 32nd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Munich, 2016
- [9] J. L. Hernández, D. Adachi, K. Yoshikawa, D. Schroos, E. van Assche, A. Feltrin, N. Valckx, N. Menou, J. Portmans, M. Yoshimi, T. Uto, H. Uzu, M. Hina, H. Kawasaki, M. Kanematsu, K. Nakano, R. Mishima, T. Kuchiyama, G. Koizumi, C. Allebé, T. Terashita, M. Hiraishi, N. Nakanishi, K. Yamamoto, "High Efficiency Copper Electroplated Heterojunction Solar Cells", 27th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Frankfurt, 2012
- [10] F. Ishimura, W. Li, E. Kobayashi, K. Hashimoto, S. Sato, Y. Watabe, E. Bende and G. Coletti, "Metal Wrap Through Heterojunction solar Cell with Plated Electrode", 32nd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, 2016
- [11] J. Heng, J. Fu, B. Kong, Y. Chae, W. Wang, Z. Xie, A. Reddy, K. Lam, C. Beitel, C. Liao, C. Erben, Z. Huang and Z. Xu, „>23.1% High Efficiency Tunnel Oxide Junction Bifacial Solar Cell with Electroplated Cu Gridlines“, 29th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, 2014
- [12] US patent number US000008236604B2
- [13] D. Adachi, T. Terashita, T. Uto, J. L. Hernández and K. Yamamoto, "Effect of SiO_x barrier layer prepared by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition on improvement of long-term reliability and production cost for Cu-plated amorphous Si/crystalline Si heterojunction solar cells", Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, 2017
- [14] European patent number EP2489076B1
- [15] A. Rodofili, W. Wolke, L. Kroely, M. Bivour, G. cimiotti, J. bartsch, M. Glathaar, J. Nekarda, "Laser-transferred Ni-seed for the Metallization of Silicon Heterojunction Solar Cells by Cu Plating", 33rd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Amsterdam, 2017
- [16] M. Balucani, K. Kholostov, P. Nenzi, R. Crescenzi, L. Serenelli, M. Izzi, M. Tucci, "New selective processing technique for solar cell", Presented at 4th Metallization Workshop, Constance, 2013
- [17] A. Lachowicz, J. Geissbühler, A. Faes, J. Champliand, J. Hermans, J.-F. Lerat, P.-J. Ribeyron, C. Roux, G. Wahli, P. Papet, B. Strahm, J. Horzel, C. Ballif and M. Despeisse, "Reliable Copper Plating Process for Bifacial Heterojunction Cells", Presented at 7^h Metallization Workshop, Constance, 2017